

Online Educational Resources Library

Co-funded by
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Cardiohealth
emotions

and

TITLE	LINK	ORGANKIT	TYPE OF RESOURCE	AUTORSHIP	LICENCE	LANGUAGE
Science Expeditions - Beatin' Heart	https://bit.ly/3Qf9Mxc	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
How a Normal Heart Pumps Blood	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JA0Wb3gc4mE	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
Sheep Heart and Model Anatomy Demo	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6Qm1fxePfAs	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	other	English
Meet the heart	https://www.khanacademy.org/science/in-in-class-10-biology/in-in-life-processes/in-in-transportation-in-human-beings/v/meet-the-heart	Cardiohealth and emotions	Visual presentation	created by others	Copyright	English
Corazón abierto maqueta fácil	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZxiS Qv4jwJQ	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	Spanish
Science Expeditions - Beatin' Heart	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vG8-kJ6sj38	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
How to Build a Model Heart Wise Wonders	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tqM BLWABMAE	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
How a Normal Heart Pumps Blood	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JA0Wb3gc4mE&t=10s	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
DIY Water filter	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=60Bi g9Ut6Mc	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
water purification (purifier) working model	https://youtu.be/Z7joDB9kGsg?si=kVeP3guok_5rF96h	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
How the heart actually pumps blood	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ruM4Xxhx32U	Cardiohealth and emotions	video	created by others	other	English
Reciprocating Pumps	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gfz IOGV9zk	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
How to Make an Air Pump	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7sLr2SY7CfQ	Cardiohealth and emotions	video	created by others	other	English
Model Heart Valves	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3X WFZRA4ICs	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English

Company develops way to make blood collection painless	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HECJvI3-rDg	Cardiohealth and emotions	video	created by others	other	English
BD PIVO Needle-free Blood Collection Device: User Instructions	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6X5D-DhCTc	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
Cardiac Conduction System and Understanding ECG, Animation.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RYZ4daFwMa8	Cardiohealth and emotions	video	created by others	other	English
A normal heartbeat	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wdbAFAip2Ow	Cardiohealth and emotions	Video	created by others	Other	English
How to be Emotionality Healthy	https://view.genial.ly/5d9f204dec5f6b0f68914f98/horizontal-infographic-lists-mental-health-day	Cardiohealth and emotions	Interactive resource	created by others	Other	English
Emotion Quiz	https://view.genial.ly/604a1f3af2f8d60d62435752/interactive-content-emotions-quiz-the-color-monster	Cardiohealth and emotions	Interactive resource	created by others	Other	English
Heart Attack	https://view.genial.ly/6097db3e8d08580d1ec2329f/presentation-heart-attack	Cardiohealth and emotions	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	English

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